

eDNAqua-Plan
NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Agreement on search criteria and system for inventorying

Milestone 2

Work Package 2

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1. Overview

Work Package 2: Audit & Gap analysis

Leaders: UniLodz/IHU

Participants: UNESCO, EMBL-EBI, UDE, UMinho, NIVA, SYKE, SSBE, INRAE

The first milestone of the eDNAqua-Plan project (M2.1), achieved in November 2023, had the aim to set out the research criteria destined to find and analyse the online DNA barcoding and eDNA projects/initiatives in Europe while providing the taxonomic, geographical, ecological and (meta)data overlap/gap analysis for the DNA barcode reference libraries and eDNA repositories.

The search criteria were set by defining specific keywords or terms that can be found in different sources, such as online databases, scientific literature, etc., and identifying types of projects that could be in scope of eDNAqua-Plan, for example, research studies, databases, initiatives, etc. This milestone sets out a crucial step for the implementation of Work Package 2 “Audit & Gap analysis” of the project.

Once the search criteria have been defined; considered as the milestone, the next step is to proceed with identification of the projects and their analysis to understand what taxa they cover (taxonomic analysis), where they are located (geographical analysis), what type of environments they take into account (ecological analysis), and what other information they associate with the genetic data (metadata analysis). As final step of Work Package 2, there will be a comparison of the diverse information of each of the identified projects while paying attention to identify their overlaps and gaps.

The search criteria for the eDNAqua-Plan project and the implementation of Work Package 2 is as follows:

No.	Name	Type	Description	Values
1	data_metadata_link	string	Explanation about how the data (sequences) are linked with its metadata. Tells if there are separate entities within the database or they are the same thing.	free text
2	record_URL	boolean	Information if there is URL or URI to the source data records. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
3	metadata_record_URL	boolean	Information if there is URL or URI or another type of link that indicates place where metadata is stored. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
4	paper_Doi_number	boolean	Information if there is DOI identifier for the paper which "delivers" the data and describes them. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
5	paper_link	boolean	Information if there is an URL or URI to the paper which "delivers" the data and describes them. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
6	DB_name	string	Official name of the database where the data is stored.	free text

7	DB_use_index	integer	Information of how often researchers are using this database estimated by analysing papers. Expressed using percentage of publications where the database name appears.	from 0 to 100
8	DB_using community	string	Explains if the database stores marine water data or fresh water data. Estimated by analysing papers that used the database.	"only fresh water","mostly fresh water","mixed","mostly marine water","only marine water"
9	number of records	integer	Total count of records in database.	integer numbers above 0
10	web_interface	boolean	Tells whether the database has interactive web interface enabling browsing and downloading available data.	true/false
11	API	boolean	Tells whether the database has API (Application Programming Interface) enabling browsing and downloading available data.	true/false
12	application	boolean	Tells whether the database supports any desktop or console application enabling browsing and downloading available data.	true/false
13	GPS_coordinates_available	boolean	Tells whether the database contains an information about GPS coordinates for samples.	true/false
14	data_export_format	string	Information about the data file formats available for download.	list of available formats
15	metadata_export_format	string	Information about the metadata file formats available for download.	list of available formats
16	env_data_contains	boolean	Tells whether the database contains the environmental samples data.	true/false
17	barcode_taxonomy_confidence	boolean	Tells whether the database has an information about confidence level of the barcode and taxonomy linkage.	true/false
18	annually_updated	boolean	Tells whether the database is updated every year.	true/false
19	data_paper_location	string	Information about where is the data available: main paper or supplement.	"main","supplement"
20	sequences_processed	string	Tells whether the sequences in database are raw or processed.	"raw","processed","both"
21	DB_standard_consisten	boolean	Tells whether the database structure is consistent	true/false
22	DB_mandatory_metadata	string	Lists metadata attributes that are necessary for the database.	list of attributes names
23	data_file_format	string	Lists the sequencing data file format the database support on upload.	list of supported formats
24	metadata_file_format	string	Lists the metadata file format the database support on upload.	list of supported formats
25	metadata_file_schema	string	Tells what is the metadata file scheme.	free text

26	DB_active	boolean	Tells whether new records being added to the database.	true/false
27	DB_curation	boolean	Tells whether there is any curation of the data in the database.	true/false
28	sample_collection	boolean	Tells if there is an information of sample collection method. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
29	DNA_extraction	boolean	Tells if there is an information of DNA extraction method. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
30	sequence_methodology	boolean	Tells if there is an information of URL to the sequence protocol in protocol.io. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
31	sequencing_strategy	boolean	Tells if there is an information of the overall sequencing strategy used in experiment. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
32	analysis_workflow	boolean	Tells if there is an information on the sequence analysis workflow. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
33	directly_uploaded	boolean	Tells whether the record was uploaded directly to the database or it was mined from another database.	true/false
34	barcode_name	string	List of barcodes using which the supplied data is sequenced.	list of barcodes names or "private"
35	barcode_certain	boolean	Does the database is doing a comparison of a barcode for certainty.	true/false
36	taxonomy_origin	string	Tells what is the reference database name used for the data taxonomical identification.	free text
37	taxonomy_URL	string	URL or URI of the reference database used for the data taxonomical identification.	HTTPS link
38	taxonomically_identified	boolean	Tells whether there is taxonomical identification in the database.	true/false
39	taxonomical_name	boolean	Tells whether there is taxonomic name for the sequences in the database.	true/false
40	taxonomy_linking	boolean	Tells whether there is any linking method the refers to some of the "big" databases e.g. after clicking in web interface.	true/false

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